

Enjoying The Coast and Connecting to Nature for Better Health: Findings from The Belgian Coast Visitors

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Abstract

The coastal nature provides unique enjoyment experiences for individuals engaged in the blue spaces. The beach sand, sea air, wave sounds, sea view, and the wideness are objects of enjoyment in the coastal setting, promoting a sense of connectedness with nature. This study aimed to examine the associations between coastal nature enjoyment and connections with the perceived health outcomes among adults visiting the Belgian coast. In addition, this study aimed to investigate the moderating effects of perceived health outcomes on the relationships between coastal nature enjoyment and connections with mental and general health conditions. By analyzing a dataset of 1,939 Flemish under the Bayesian Mindsponge Framework, this study found that almost all types of coastal nature enjoyment and connection were positively associated with perceived health outcomes, except for enjoying the beach sand, which showed an unclear association. Enjoying the sea wideness was positively associated with perceived mental health, while enjoying the wave sounds showed a negative association. Enjoying sea view and wideness, and the beach sand were positively associated with perceived general health, while enjoying the sea air and wave sounds showed negative associations. The perceived health outcomes showed positive moderating effects on the relationships between coastal nature enjoyment and connections with mental and general health conditions.

Keywords: coastal nature; nature enjoyment; nature connection; health outcomes; mental health; general health.

Her entire being is like an ethereal painting, a playful creation of nature using colors, lines, dots, strokes, and patches. One can only exclaim, "Absolutely enchanting. Is this real or an illusion?"

—In "The Philosophy of Awakening;" Wild Wise Weird (Q.-H. Vuong, 2024)

1. Introduction

Human well-being is increasingly understood to be intertwined with nature. Nature's role in promoting health and well-being has gained substantial attention in recent years (Bell et al., 2019), with a growing body of research linking natural environments with stress reduction, mood enhancement, and cognitive functioning (Berto, 2014); improvement of physical and mental health, and overall well-being (Dyment & Green, 2020; MacKerron & Mourato, 2013; Wells, 2021). Being in nature appears to protect

individuals against the impacts of stressors and offers physiological, emotional, and attentional restoration beyond what urban settings provide (Berto, 2014). In particular, coastal settings have long been used for leisure and healing (e.g. thalassotherapy since the 18th century) and are now being empirically recognized as environments that can positively influence well-being (Severin et al., 2022).

Within this broader context, coastal environments have attracted special attention as uniquely beneficial “blue spaces” rich in sensory stimuli. Coastal environments possess unique characteristics, such as visual aesthetics, sounds, and air quality, that may amplify their health-promoting effects (Subiza-Pérez et al., 2020). The sight of open water and horizon, the sound of waves and seabirds, the smell of sea air, and the feel of sand and sea breeze are unique features of coastal nature with restorative and therapeutic potentials. Evidence has shown that the sound of waves was a potential contributor to the restorative effects of coastal environments (Subiza-Pérez et al., 2020). Compared to green spaces, the sensory richness and distinct atmosphere of coastal environments may provide an extra level of relaxation and fascination that contributes to human health and well-being in unique ways. Indeed, evidence suggests that individuals visiting the coast at least twice weekly tended to have better self-reported general and mental health than those with infrequent visits (Hooyberg et al., 2024). Coastal environments, or “blue spaces”, are increasingly recognized as significant contributors to human well-being, particularly in the context of rapid urbanization and growing mental health challenges globally (Grellier et al., 2017).

In this study, we focus on two key psychosocial dimensions of people’s experiences with coastal environments: enjoyment and connection. Enjoyment of coastal environments refers to the degree of pleasure, positive emotion, and personal satisfaction one derives from visiting and spending time at the coast (Kelly, 2018). It encompasses the immediate happiness or relaxation one feels – for instance, the joy of a sunny beach day or the sense of calm from watching ocean waves (Ugbekile & Chaigneau, 2024). Connection to nature, on the other hand, refers to one’s subjective sense of kinship or oneness with the natural world (Schilowitz, 2023), often termed nature connectedness or nature relatedness. It reflects how integrated a person feels with nature in general or with specific natural places like the seaside (Ives et al., 2017). Higher nature connection is associated with greater psychological well-being and positive emotions (Capaldi et al., 2014), indicating that feeling connected to the coastal environment might amplify the benefits gained from it.

We also introduce the concept of perceived health outcomes from coastal visits – that is, the health benefits individuals believe they have gained as a result of their interactions with coastal environments, which were self-reported. This is based on the health belief model encompassing concepts of perceived health benefits, perceived illness severity, perceived health outcomes, cues to action, and trust in healthcare (Wong et al., 2021). Perceived health outcomes from coastal visits could include improvements in mood, stress levels, energy, or overall fitness that people attribute to their beach visits over the past year. Such self-reported health outcomes are subjective, but they are important; research shows that self-rated health is a reliable indicator of actual health status and even a predictor of long-term health outcomes (DeSalvo et al., 2006). In our context, perceived health outcomes serve as a potential link between one's coastal experiences and their broader health status.

Finally, we distinguish between two facets of health: mental health and general health. Mental health encompasses emotional regulation and well-being, psychological distress or problems, such as anxiety/depression, and cognitive functioning (Gkintoni et al., 2025). General health encompasses overall health status and general well-being, including physical health and health-related quality of life (Karimi & Brazier, 2016). Both mental and general health can be influenced by lifestyle (Atzendorf et al., 2018) and environmental factors (Kim & Kim, 2017), and they represent crucial outcomes in public health research. The main health effects promoted by a visit to the coast appear to be the restorative effects, linked to mental health (Kruizinga, 2016), while coastal visit frequency may benefit health because it promotes longer bouts of and/or higher intensity forms of physical activity, linked to physical health (Elliott et al., 2015; Geiger et al., 2023).

While the health-promoting qualities of coastal environments are well-documented, most studies to date have focused on broad measures of health benefits without delving into the mediating factors or granular psychological processes underlying these effects. There is limited understanding of the mechanisms linking coastal environment enjoyment and specific connections to health outcomes. Moreover, previous research has primarily examined immediate effects rather than longer-term health impacts and often lacks a robust theoretical framework for understanding how people process and internalize their coastal experiences. A systematic review highlighted the need for more rigorous research to establish causal relationships between blue space interventions and health outcomes (Britton et al., 2020).

Additionally, while short-term restorative effects of nature are well-established, it remains unclear how granular cognitive interactions with the environment shape long-term health outcomes. In other words, what are the mental processes by which many small positive experiences (like each relaxing coastal visit) accumulate into a person's year-round perception of their health? The Granular Interaction Thinking Theory (GITT) provides a conceptual hint that these micro-interactions matter (Q.-H. Vuong et al., 2025), but empirical research has yet to illuminate this process in the context of health and nature. This leads to our second gap: the potential mediating role of perceived health outcomes. No prior study has definitively shown whether believing that one's health has improved due to nature exposure actually mediates the relationship between nature experiences and measured health status. If, for example, enjoying the beach leads someone to *feel* healthier (perceived outcome), does that feeling itself contribute to better mental health (perhaps by reducing worry, increasing optimism, or encouraging healthy behavior)? This mediation perspective is novel in the nature-health literature, and addressing it can deepen our understanding of cause-effect pathways.

The third gap lies in methodology – specifically, capturing the above cognitive mechanisms with appropriate modeling. Traditional statistical models might oversimplify or miss the latent cognitive variables at play. The Bayesian Mindsponge Framework (BMF), however, is well-suited to model complex mental processes like information filtering and belief updating (Nguyen et al., 2022). Until now, BMF has not been applied to examine environmental experiences and health, so this study also tackles the unknown of whether a Bayesian mindsponge-based model can effectively represent the cognitive decision-making and belief formation underlying environmental health benefits. To note, BMF has been successfully applied in several environmental studies, such as understanding the exchange of monetary and environmental values (Q. H. Vuong, 2021), understanding the aesthetic and diversity values of plants and pets in shaping biodiversity loss belief (Q.-H. Vuong et al., 2024), etc., and in several health studies, such as understanding the COVID-19 vaccines production process through the perspective of the serendipity-mindsponge-3D creativity management theory (Q.-H. Vuong, Le, et al., 2022), understanding the influence of educational attainment and custom rules adherence on health consideration in food consumption (Sari et al., 2025), etc. Thus, BMF has the potential to shed light on the complex interplay between coastal environments and human health.

Given this background, the present study aims to explore the relationships between coastal nature enjoyment and connection with health-related outcomes. We hope to shed light on the cognitive and psychological factors that link coastal nature experiences, in

terms of enjoyment and connection, with tangible health outcomes, in terms of mental and general health, in a longer-term perspective. This focus extends beyond documenting the immediate effects of a beach outing (like lower stress at the time) and instead examines a longer-term perspective: health outcomes “over the past year,” as reported by participants, in relation to their enjoyment of and connection to coastal nature.

Based on the identified gaps and the aims of our study, we formulate the following research questions (RQs):

1. How are enjoyment and connection to coastal environments associated with perceived health outcomes over the past year? – This question examines whether individuals who report greater enjoyment of coastal visits and a stronger connection to nature also report more positive health outcomes that they attribute to those coastal experiences in the last year. We seek to determine the direction and strength of these associations.
2. How are perceived health outcomes associated with mental health and general health? – Here we ask whether individuals who perceive greater health benefits from their coastal visits also tend to have better long-term mental health and general health status. Essentially, we examine if perceiving positive outcomes (like feeling healthier or less stressed thanks to coastal trips) correlates with one’s actual mental well-being and overall health rating.
3. Do perceived health outcomes mediate the relationships between coastal enjoyment/connection and mental/general health? – This question probes the potential intermediary role of perceived health benefits. We investigate whether the effect of coastal enjoyment and nature connection on mental and general health operates indirectly through perceived health outcomes. In other words, is it the case that enjoying and feeling connected to the coast leads to better perceived health, which in turn leads to better mental and general health?

Corresponding to these questions, the objectives of the study are:

1. To analyze the relationship between coastal environment enjoyment/connection and self-perceived health benefits from coastal visits.
2. To explore the linkage between those perceived health outcomes and longer-term mental health and general health status.
3. To examine whether the perceived health outcomes function as a mediating factor in the pathway from coastal enjoyment/connection to mental and general health.

Through these objectives, we aim to construct and test a conceptual model that connects a person's experience and attitudes during coastal nature exposure (enjoyment, connection) with their subjective and objective health indicators, thereby fulfilling the goal of understanding both direct and indirect effects in this human–nature–health dynamic.

2. Methods

2.1. Theoretical Foundation

Two key theoretical frameworks often invoked to explain these study outcomes are Attention Restoration Theory (ART) and Stress Recovery Theory (SRT). ART was developed by Kaplan and Kaplan in 1989. It addresses the cognitive side of individual experience (Kaplan & Kaplan, 1989). Four characteristics define a restorative environment in ART: being away (a mental escape from routine), extent (richness and coherence of the environment), fascination (automatically engaging interest), and compatibility (fit with one's purposes) (Kaplan & Kaplan, 1989). When these are present – as they often are at a tranquil beach or scenic coast – the individual can recover their attentional capacity and feel mentally refreshed. Coastal natural environments, by their inherently fascinating stimuli (waves, sands, birds, sea breeze, etc.), gently capture our involuntary attention, allowing directed attention to rest. ART proposes that modern life overloads our directed attention (the effortful attention used for work, screens, and tasks), leading to mental fatigue. Empirical support for ART comes from studies showing that engaging with softly fascinating stimuli like a gently rippling tide allows our directed attention (which is finite and easily fatigued) to rest and recover (Liu et al., 2024). This leads to reduced mental fatigue and improved focus after coastal visits.

Similarly, SRT posits that exposure to unthreatening natural environments automatically evokes positive affective responses and lowers stress arousal, as an evolutionary adaptive reaction (Liu et al., 2024). SRT, first introduced by Ulrich in 1983, focuses on the affective and physiological responses to nature (Ulrich, 2023). SRT views that when an individual is stressed, viewing or being in a soothing natural environment elicits an involuntary positive emotional response (e.g., interest, calm) that swiftly reduces stress levels. Empirical support for SRT comes from studies showing that even brief encounters with nature (like looking at greenery through a window or a short walk in a park) can lead to measurable physiological stress recovery: reduced blood pressure, muscle tension, and

cortisol levels, often within minutes (Berto, 2014). In sum, SRT emphasizes nature's role in immediate stress reduction through unconscious emotional responses (Ulrich, 2023), while ART emphasizes attention restoration and cognitive recovery through engaging yet non-demanding stimuli (Kaplan & Kaplan, 1989). Notably, these theories are not mutually exclusive; they likely operate together, and both are grounded in the idea that humans respond positively to natural cues (biophilia). Together, ART and SRT explain much of the short-term benefits one gains during or shortly after a nature experience, such as a calmer mood and sharper mind following a seaside stroll.

In building our approach, we introduce the Granular Interaction Thinking Theory (GITT) as a complementary framework alongside the established ART and SRT. While ART and SRT provide insight into the short-term restorative and stress-reducing effects of nature exposure, they do not explicitly address how these benefits may build up or persist in the long run. GITT offers a novel perspective by considering each person–environment interaction as a discrete “granular” information exchange that can cumulatively shape an individual's mindset or values (Q.-H. Vuong et al., 2025). Originating from an integration of quantum mechanics principles, information theory, and the mindsponge cognitive model, GITT suggests that the mind continuously absorbs and processes information from the environment in bits or quanta, gradually reorganizing itself to adapt and thrive (Q.-H. Vuong et al., 2025).

In our context, each enjoyable encounter with the coastal environment can be seen as one unit of positive information that the mind takes in. Repeated coastal experiences (each rich in sensory input and emotional reward) may reinforce certain cognitions – for example, the belief that “being by the sea is good for me” – which over time could influence one's overall perception of their health and well-being. By applying GITT, we aim to capture these long-term, cumulative cognitive effects of coastal visits that traditional theories might overlook.

While GITT helps explain long-term internalization, we align it with ART and SRT to cover the full spectrum of effects. In the short term, as noted, ART explains how a single coastal visit can restore attention (Ohly et al., 2016), and SRT explains how it can alleviate stress (Ulrich, 2023). GITT does not contradict these; rather, it complements them by asking what happens when such restorative experiences are repeated and accumulated. We propose that through the GITT perspective, the benefits described by ART and SRT (e.g., regained concentration, uplifted mood) are not fleeting; instead, they are encoded

as valuable information in the mindsponge mechanism (Q.-H. Vuong, 2023). With each beneficial visit, the mindsponge (a metaphor for the mind's filtering mechanism) may become more *receptive* to nature (since prior positive outcomes lower resistance to new similar information) and incorporate the notion that "coastal visits = good outcomes" into the core mindset. Over many interactions, this could manifest as an improved general outlook on health or increased resilience to stress even outside of nature. In essence, ART and SRT operate at the episode level, whereas GITT provides insight at the cumulative level – bridging from episodes to enduring dispositions.

Within this theoretical foundation, we articulate three hypotheses corresponding to our research questions:

- H1: Enjoyment of coastal environments and connection to nature are positively associated with perceived health outcomes from coastal visits. In other words, individuals who report higher enjoyment and a stronger sense of connection during their coastal experiences will also report greater perceived health benefits from those experiences (e.g., more improvement in mood, energy, stress levels over the past year attributable to coastal visits).
- H2: Perceived health outcomes from coastal visits are positively associated with individuals' mental health and general health. That is, those who perceive more positive health effects from their coastal trips tend to have better mental health (e.g., lower psychological distress, higher well-being) and better general health status. We expect perceived outcomes to correlate with these health measures, consistent with the idea that how healthy one feels can reflect and influence how healthy one is.
- H3: Perceived health outcomes mediate the relationships between coastal enjoyment/connection and mental health/general health. This hypothesis proposes an indirect effect: enjoyment of and connection to the coast contribute to improved mental and general health *through* the mechanism of perceived health outcomes. In statistical terms, we anticipate that when controlling for perceived outcomes, the direct associations of enjoyment or connection with mental/general health will attenuate, indicating that part of their effect is channeled via the individual's perception of health benefits. This mediation would support the idea that repeatedly feeling better after coastal visits translates into a lasting health advantage.

These hypotheses integrate the theoretical perspectives discussed: H1 is grounded in the notion that positive, meaningful interactions (enjoyment, connection) yield valuable internal outcomes (perceived benefits), H2 aligns with literature that self-perceptions of health relate to actual health metrics, and H3 synthesizes everything by suggesting a pathway consistent with both restorative theory of ART and SRT (enjoyment/connection yield immediate benefits) and GITT (immediate benefits must be internalized/perceived to affect long-term health).

2.2. Model Construction

2.2.1. Dataset

This study utilized data from a comprehensive survey of 1,939 Flemish-speaking Belgian residents and their recreational visits to the Belgian coast (Hooyberg et al., 2024). The data was collected from January 2nd to January 17th, 2023, using quota sampling based on age (<34y, 35-49y, 50-64y, >65y), sex, province, and educational attainment (low, middle, high). The survey was conducted in Dutch using the Bpact user interface and Qualtrics software, with a panel of 30,000 to 35,000 Flemish-speaking participants from five provinces in Flanders. The survey questionnaire included four main sections. The first section contained questions about coastal visits, which varied based on respondents' visit history to the Belgian coast in the previous year or before that. The second section focused on demographic background, the third on socio-economic status, and the fourth on health status (Hooyberg et al., 2024). A more detailed explanation of Hooyberg's study and the associated dataset is accessible online via this web address: <https://www.nature.com/articles/s41597-024-03161-y>

From the total 2,574 responses collected, 1,939 participants provided complete responses. The respondents received points from the panel provider, which could be exchanged for monetary compensation. The research adhered to the ethical guidelines established by the Faculty of Psychology and Educational Sciences at Ghent University, ensuring anonymous participation with consent obtained through panel subscription. The questionnaires and dataset are publicly accessible through IMIS: <https://doi.org/10.14284/625>.

2.2.2. Variable Selection and Rationale

For the current study, we employed 11 variables to construct the model from the dataset, including three outcome variables and eight predictor variables (see Table 1).

BetterHealthAtCoast, *MentalHealth*, *GeneralHealth* are the outcome variables. The variable *BetterHealthAtCoast* was constructed as a composite measure of perceived health benefits during previous years' coastal visits. This composite was calculated as the mean score of four health-related items (Cronbach's alpha = 0.886), encompassing both physical and mental aspects of health: How often does the following experience apply to you during the previous year? – Feeling physical rest; - Relax; - Find mental peace; - Feel happier. Each question was measured on a five-point Likert scale ('never', 'seldom', 'sometimes', 'often', 'always'), with higher scores indicating greater perceived health benefits at the coast. *MentalHealth* evaluates the presence of any long-term mental illness or disorder (formally diagnosed by a psychiatrist), while *GeneralHealth* represents individual evaluation on the general health condition during the past year. Detailed variable descriptions are provided in Table 1.

Table 1. Variable description

Variable	Description	Type of variable	Value
<i>BetterHealthAtCoast</i>	The average value of four items asking about the respondents' perception of health outcomes during previous year's coastal visits	Numerical	Min = 1 Max = 5
<i>MentalHealth</i>	The presence of any long-term mental illness or disorder (formally diagnosed by a psychiatrist).	Binary	1 = No; 2 = Yes
<i>GeneralHealth</i>	Self-assessment on the general health during the past year.	Numerical	1 = Very good; 2 = Good; 3 = Moderate; 4 = Bad; 5 = Very bad

<i>EnjoyingSandToes</i>	Whether the respondent enjoyed the sand between toes during coastal visits	Numerical	1 = Never; 2 = Seldom; 3 = Sometimes; 4 = Often; 5 = Always
<i>EnjoyingSeaAir</i>	Whether the respondent enjoyed the sea air during coastal visits	Numerical	1 = Never; 2 = Seldom; 3 = Sometimes; 4 = Often; 5 = Always
<i>EnjoyingSoundOfWaves</i>	Whether the respondent enjoyed the sound of waves during coastal visits	Numerical	1 = Never; 2 = Seldom; 3 = Sometimes; 4 = Often; 5 = Always
<i>EnjoyingTheView</i>	Whether the respondent enjoyed the view during coastal visits	Numerical	1 = Never; 2 = Seldom; 3 = Sometimes; 4 = Often; 5 = Always
<i>EnjoyingExtent</i>	Whether the respondent enjoyed the wideness during coastal visits	Numerical	1 = Never; 2 = Seldom; 3 = Sometimes; 4 = Often; 5 = Always
<i>ConnectingWithNature</i>	The extent to which the respondent feels a sense of connection with nature during coastal visits	Numerical	1 = Never; 2 = Seldom; 3 = Sometimes; 4 = Often; 5 = Always
<i>FeelingCompatible</i>	The extent to which the respondent feels compatible with the	Numerical	1 = Never; 2 = Seldom; 3 = Sometimes; 4 =

	environment during coastal visits		Often; 5 = Always
<i>BeingFascinated</i>	The extent to which the respondent feels fascinated by the environment during coastal visits	Numerical	1 = Never; 2 = Seldom; 3 = Sometimes; 4 = Often; 5 = Always

2.2.3. Statistical Models

To test our hypotheses and ensuring that our analysis can capture the nuanced relationships and theoretical constructs involved, we built several parsimonious models.

To test the relationship between visitors' enjoyment and connection to the coastal environment and their perceived health outcomes during the previous year's coastal visit, we constructed Model 1 with the following structure:

$$BetterHealthAtCoast_i \sim normal(\mu_i, \sigma) \quad (1.1)$$

$$\mu_i = \beta_0 + \beta_1 * EnjoyingSandToes_i + \beta_2 * EnjoyingSeaAir_i + \beta_3 * EnjoyingSoundOfWaves_i + \beta_4 * EnjoyingTheView_i + \beta_5 * ConnectingWithNature_i + \beta_6 * EnjoyingExtent_i + \beta_7 * FeelingCompatible_i + \beta_8 * BeingFascinated_i \quad (1.2)$$

$$\beta \sim normal(M, S) \quad (1.3)$$

In Model 1, μ_i represents the expected level of perceived health outcomes during coastal visits for individual i , predicted based on 8 variables measuring their enjoyment of and connection to the coastal environment. The coefficients β capture the relationship between each predictor (e.g., enjoying the sound of waves, connecting with nature) and the outcome variable *BetterHealthAtCoast*, and are distributed normally with a mean M and a standard deviation S . The variability of outcome not explained by the predictors is modeled as a normally distributed noise term with standard deviation σ . The model is illustrated in Figure 1 below.

Figure 1. The logical network of the constructed Model 1

Next, to test the relationship between perceived health outcomes during the previous year's coastal visits and the visitors' mental health, we constructed Model 2 with the following structure:

$$GeneralHealth_i \sim normal(\mu_i, \sigma) \quad (2.1)$$

$$\mu_i = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \times BetterHealthAtCoast_i \quad (2.2)$$

$$\beta \sim normal(M, S) \quad (2.3)$$

In Model 2, μ_i represents the self-reported general health of individual i during the previous year, predicted based on their perception of health outcomes during the previous year's coastal visit ($BetterHealthAtCoast$). The coefficients β follow normal distributions with a mean M and a standard deviation S . The residual variability of mental health not explained by the predictor is captured by σ . If β_1 is significant, it suggests that perceived health outcomes during coastal visits are associated with the individual's general health status. The model is illustrated in Figure 2 below.

Figure 2. The logical network of the constructed Model 2

To test the relationship between perceived health outcomes during the previous year's coastal visits and the visitors' perceived general health, we constructed Model 3 with the following structure:

$$MentalHealth_i \sim normal(\mu_i, \sigma) \quad (3.1)$$

$$\mu_i = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \times BetterHealthAtCoast_i \quad (3.2)$$

$$\beta \sim normal(M, S) \quad (3.3)$$

In Model 3, μ_i represents the self-reported mental health of individual i based on the SF36 Mental Health Inventory, predicted based on their perception of health outcomes during the previous year's coastal visit (*BetterHealthAtCoast*). The coefficients β follow normal distributions with a mean M and a standard deviation S . The residual variability of mental health not explained by the predictor is captured by σ . If the coefficient β_1 is significant, it would suggest that individuals who perceive greater health benefits from coastal visits tend to report better mental health status, controlling for other factors. The model is illustrated in Figure 3 below.

Figure 3. The logical network of the constructed Model 3

To test the association of various aspects of visitor's coastal experiences and their perception of health outcomes during the previous year's coastal visit to visitor's mental health, we constructed Model 4 with the following structure:

$$MentalHealth_i \sim normal(\mu_i, \sigma) \quad (4.1)$$

$$\mu_i = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \times EnjoyingSandToes_i + \beta_2 \times EnjoyingSeaAir_i + \beta_3 \times EnjoyingSoundOfWaves_i + \beta_4 \times EnjoyingTheView_i + \beta_5 \times ConnectingWithNature_i + \beta_6 \times EnjoyingExtent_i + \beta_7 \times FeelingCompatible_i + \beta_8 \times BeingFascinated_i + \beta_9 \times BetterHealthAtCoast_i \quad (4.2)$$

$$\beta \sim normal(M, S) \quad (4.3)$$

In Model 4, μ_i represents the self-reported mental health of individual i based on the SF36 Mental Health Inventory, predicted based on 9 variables measuring their enjoyment and connection to various aspects of the coastal environment, as well as their perception of health outcomes during the previous year's coastal visit. The coefficients β follow normal distributions with a mean M and a standard deviation S . The residual variability of mental

health not explained by the predictor is captured by σ . If the coefficient β_1 through β_9 are significant, it would suggest that individuals who enjoy various aspects of the coastal environment and perceive greater health benefits from coastal visits tend to report better mental health status, controlling for other factors. The model is illustrated in Figure 4 below.

Figure 4. The logical network of the constructed Model 4

Finally, to test the association of various aspects of visitors' coastal experiences and their perception of health outcomes during the previous year's coastal visit to visitors' perceived general health, we constructed Model 5 with the following structure:

$$GeneralHealth_i \sim normal(\mu_i, \sigma) \quad (5.1)$$

$$\mu_i = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \times EnjoyingSandToes_i + \beta_2 \times EnjoyingSeaAir_i + \beta_3 \times EnjoyingSoundOfWaves_i + \beta_4 \times EnjoyingTheView_i + \beta_5 \times ConnectingWithNature_i + \beta_6 \times EnjoyingExtent_i + \beta_7 \times FeelingCompatible_i + \beta_8 \times BeingFascinated_i + \beta_9 \times BetterHealthAtCoast_i \quad (5.2)$$

$$\beta \sim normal(M, S) \quad (5.3)$$

In Model 5, μ_i represents the self-reported general health of individual i during the previous year, predicted based on nine variables that measure their enjoyment and connection to various aspects of the coastal environment, as well as their perception of health outcomes during the previous year's coastal visit. The coefficients β follow normal distributions with a mean M and a standard deviation S . The residual variability of mental

health not explained by the predictor is captured by σ . If the coefficient β_1 through β_9 are significant, it would suggest that individuals who enjoy various aspects of the coastal environment and perceive greater health benefits from coastal visits tend to report better general health, controlling for other factors. The model is illustrated in Figure 5 below.

Figure 5. The logical network of the constructed Model 5

2.3. Data Analysis and Validation

To investigate the proposed models, we applied BMF analytics, an approach well-suited for modeling complex cognitive and behavioral data (Nguyen et al., 2022). BMF analytics proceeds by first conceptualizing the research problem using the mindsponge mechanism (Q.-H. Vuong, 2023) – essentially mapping our hypotheses onto a cognitive information-processing model – and then constructing a Bayesian statistical model that corresponds to this conceptual map (Q.-H. Vuong, Nguyen, et al., 2022). Thus, BMF analytics integrates the inferential strengths of Bayesian analysis with the logical reasoning capabilities of GITT, the updated Mindsponge Theory (Q.-H. Vuong, La, et al., 2022; Q.-H. Vuong et al., 2025). The flexibility of BMF method, as noted by its proponents, allows inclusion of non-linear relationships or interactions if theory suggests (for instance, maybe the effect of enjoyment on health plateaus at very high levels – we could model that non-linearity in Bayesian terms). However, for clarity, we are focusing on linear associations as per our hypotheses.

In our case, the mindsponge-based conceptualization views variables like coastal enjoyment and nature connection as inputs of information that individuals absorb, with

perceived health outcomes as an intermediate belief or evaluation that forms within the mind, eventually influencing outputs like mental health status. This conceptual structure is translated into a Bayesian hierarchical model. The model is hierarchical because we acknowledge that data are collected from individuals who may vary in their baseline health and in how strongly they experience enjoyment or connection. For instance, one person's "high enjoyment" might still be different in absolute terms from another person's "high enjoyment." A hierarchical Bayesian model can include random intercepts (to account for individual differences in baseline health ratings) and potentially random slopes (to account for individual differences in the effect of enjoyment or connection on perceived outcomes) (Q.-H. Vuong, Nguyen, et al., 2022).

Bayesian inference provides notable advantages, such as the use of credible intervals for interpreting results instead of relying on confidence intervals and p-values when compared to the frequentist approach (Halsey et al., 2015; Wagenmakers et al., 2018). Another advantage of the Bayesian approach is that we can directly estimate the *mediated effect* as a parameter (the product of two path coefficients) and derive a credibility interval for it, rather than relying on asymptotic approximations (Q.-H. Vuong, Nguyen, et al., 2022). This aligns well with our mediation hypothesis (H3). Additionally, the Bayesian framework naturally incorporates individual variability: rather than fixed "one-size-fits-all" coefficients, we treat effects as distributions. For example, our analysis will yield a distribution for the association between enjoyment and perceived health outcome, reflecting uncertainty and variation, instead of a single p-value. Furthermore, the Markov Chain Monte Carlo (MCMC) method allows Bayesian analysis to handle complex models, including multilevel and nonlinear regression frameworks (Dunson, 2001). By using Bayesian inference via MCMC sampling, we can obtain posterior distributions for all parameters, including regression coefficients for paths (enjoyment → perceived outcome, connection → perceived outcome, perceived outcome → health, etc.) and for indirect effects (enjoyment → perceived outcome → health).

Bayesian inference probabilistically can address both known and unknown properties, enabling the development of concise models (Csilléry et al., 2010; Rodrigues & Iemma, 2014). When developing a Bayesian model, it is crucial to carefully choose the appropriate prior distribution. If prior research or expert knowledge offers guidance on expected effect sizes (perhaps prior studies suggest a small-to-moderate effect of nature connectedness on well-being), we can use informative priors in the model to make our estimates more robust, though in absence of strong priors we will use non-informative or

weakly informative priors to let the data speak largely for themselves. In this investigation, we opted for uninformative priors or a flat prior distribution to reduce the amount of prior information available for model estimation, as the study was exploratory in nature (McElreath, 2020).

The models were fitted using three Markov chains. Each chain had 2000 warmup iterations and 5000 total iterations. After successful model fitting, we used Pareto-smoothed importance sampling leave-one-out (PSIS-LOO) diagnostics to evaluate the goodness of fit of the models (Vehtari & Gabry, 2024). The LOO computation procedure is outlined as follows:

$$LOO = -2LPPD_{loo} = -2 \sum \log \int p(y_i | \theta) p_{(post(-i)(\theta))} d$$

The posterior distribution $p_{post(-i)}(\theta)$ is calculated from the data, excluding data point i . The k-Pareto values are used in the PSIS method to perform leave-one-out cross-validation, which helps identify observations that significantly impact the PSIS estimate. Observations with k-Pareto values exceeding 0.7 are considered influential and may pose difficulties in performing leave-one-out cross-diagnostics to assess the model's goodness of fit. Models are generally considered to fit the data well when k values are below 0.5 (Vehtari et al., 2017).

Once the data are well-aligned with the model, we can move forward to assess convergence diagnostics and interpret the findings. Statistical and visual techniques can be employed to assess the convergence of Markov chains. The effective sample size (n_{eff}) and the Gelman–Rubin shrink factor ($Rhat$) are commonly used to assess convergence (Gelman & Rubin, 1992). The n_{eff} value represents the number of independent samples during the simulation process. Convergence is generally considered achieved when n_{eff} exceeds 1000, indicating a sufficient number of samples for reliable inferences (McElreath, 2020). Further, the $Rhat$ value is a measure of the potential scale reduction factor. A $Rhat$ is greater than 1.1 signifies the model has not converged, while a $Rhat$ value of 1 indicates the model has converged. Visual validation of Markov chain convergence can also be used by examining trace plots, Gelman–Rubin–Brooks plots, and autocorrelation plots (McElreath, 2020).

The data analysis can be conducted using a suitable Bayesian software environment (such as JAGS or Stan via R platform, or the dedicated **bayesvl** package developed for BMF applications) (La et al., 2022; Q.-H. Vuong et al., 2020), ensuring that convergence

diagnostics, e.g., Rhat statistics, and posterior predictive checks are examined for model validation. Our Bayesian analysis was conducted using the **bayesvl** package, which was built on the R platform (La et al., 2022; Q.-H. Vuong et al., 2020). The dataset, data description, and code snippets related to our Bayesian analysis are available at <https://zenodo.org/records/13844709>

3. Results

Before interpreting the results, evaluating how well Model 1, 4, and 5 fit the data is necessary. As can be seen in Figures 6a, 6b, and 6c below, all estimated k-values are below the 0.7 threshold as the recommended value, indicating a good fit signal between the models and the data.

Figure 6a. Model 1’s PSIS-LOO diagnosis: The enjoyment of and connection to the coastal environment and the perceived health outcomes during the previous year’s coastal visits

Figure 6b. Model 4's PSIS-LOO diagnosis: The enjoyment of & connection to the coastal environment and visitors' mental health

Figure 6c. Model 5's PSIS-LOO diagnosis: The enjoyment of & connection to the coastal environment and visitors' perceived general health

The posterior distribution statistics of all Models are shown in Table 2 below. All n_{eff} values are higher than 1000, except for Model 3, indicating effective samples for reliable inference. The Rhat values of 1 in all models do not indicate the well-convergence conditions between Markov chains because all models were constructed within a single chain.

Table 2: Estimated results of all Models

Model	Parameters	Mean	SD	n_eff	Rhat
1	<i>a_BetterHealthAtCoast</i>	0.54	0.05	3056	1
	<i>b_BeingFascinated_BetterHealthAtCoast</i>	0.09	0.02	3484	1
	<i>b_FeelingCompatible_BetterHealthAtCoast</i>	0.20	0.01	3366	1
	<i>b_EnjoyingExtent_BetterHealthAtCoast</i>	0.05	0.01	3261	1
	<i>b_ConnectingWithNature_BetterHealthAtCoast</i>	0.13	0.01	3148	1
	<i>b_EnjoyingTheView_BetterHealthAtCoast</i>	0.09	0.02	3412	1
	<i>b_EnjoyingSoundOfWaves_BetterHealthAtCoast</i>	0.10	0.02	3163	1
	<i>b_EnjoyingSeaAir_BetterHealthAtCoast</i>	0.20	0.02	2770	1
	<i>b_EnjoyingSandToes_BetterHealthAtCoast</i>	0.01	0.01	3661	1
2	<i>a_MentalHealth</i>	34.67	0.69	1132	1
	<i>b_BetterHealthAtCoast_MentalHealth</i>	0.68	0.19	1135	1
3	<i>a_GeneralHealth</i>	3.56	0.08	946	1
	<i>b_BetterHealthAtCoast_GeneralHealth</i>	0.03	0.02	906	1
4	<i>a_MentalHealth</i>	35.17	0.85	4409	1
	<i>b_BetterHealthAtCoast_MentalHealth</i>	0.63	0.28	4018	1
	<i>b_BeingFascinated_MentalHealth</i>	0.22	0.22	4186	1
	<i>b_FeelingCompatible_MentalHealth</i>	0.02	0.20	3563	1
	<i>b_EnjoyingExtent_MentalHealth</i>	0.64	0.20	3276	1

	<i>b_ConnectingWithNature_MentalHealth</i>	-0.08	0.21	3328	1
	<i>b_EnjoyingTheView_MentalHealth</i>	-0.12	0.25	4342	1
	<i>b_EnjoyingSoundOfWaves_MentalHealth</i>	-0.56	0.21	3669	1
	<i>b_EnjoyingSeaAir_MentalHealth</i>	-0.02	0.23	3750	1
	<i>b_EnjoyingSandToes_MentalHealth</i>	-0.14	0.15	4171	1
5	<i>a_GeneralHealth</i>	3.59	0.10	3774	1
	<i>b_BetterHealthAtCoast_GeneralHealth</i>	0.02	0.04	3066	1
	<i>b_BeingFascinated_GeneralHealth</i>	0.01	0.03	3890	1
	<i>b_FeelingCompatible_GeneralHealth</i>	0.00	0.03	3329	1
	<i>b_EnjoyingExtent_GeneralHealth</i>	0.04	0.02	3932	1
	<i>b_ConnectingWithNature_GeneralHealth</i>	-0.01	0.03	3877	1
	<i>b_EnjoyingTheView_GeneralHealth</i>	0.03	0.03	3123	1
	<i>b_EnjoyingSoundOfWaves_GeneralHealth</i>	-0.05	0.03	3661	1
	<i>b_EnjoyingSeaAir_GeneralHealth</i>	-0.03	0.03	3359	1
	<i>b_EnjoyingSandToes_GeneralHealth</i>	0.01	0.02	3366	1

Figures 7, 8, and 9 illustrate the estimated posterior distributions of Model 1, 4, and 5, respectively. As can be seen in Figure 7, almost all distributions of the enjoyment of and connection to the coastal environment are located on the positive side of the x-axis, except for *b_EnjoyingSandToes*. These conditions indicate that almost all types of enjoyment of and connection to the coastal environment are positively associated with the perceived health outcomes during the previous year's coastal visits, and these associations are highly reliable. Conversely, enjoying the sand between toes during coastal visits shows an unclear association with the perceived health outcomes (see Figure 7).

Figure 8 shows that the perceived health outcomes during the previous year's coastal visits are positively associated with visitors' mental health, indicating that the perceived health outcomes positively moderate the relationship between the enjoyment of and connection to the coastal environment with visitors' mental health. Whether the

respondent enjoyed the wideness during coastal visits is also positively associated with perceived mental health. Oppositely, whether the respondent enjoyed the sound of waves during coastal visits is negatively associated with visitors' mental health. These associations are highly reliable. In addition, other types of enjoyment of and connection to the coastal environment show ambiguous associations with perceived mental health (see Figure 8).

Figure 9 shows that the perceived health outcomes have a moderate positive association with visitors' general health. Whether the respondent enjoyed the wideness, the view, and the sand between toes during coastal visits are positively associated with perceived general health. Oppositely, whether the respondent enjoyed the sea air and the sound of waves during coastal visits are negatively associated with general health. The extent to which the respondent feels a sense of connection with nature during coastal visits also shows a negative association (see Figure 9). All associations illustrated in Figure 9 are moderately reliable.

Figure 7. Model 1's estimated coefficients: The enjoyment of and connection to the coastal environment and the perceived health outcomes

Figure 8. Model 4's estimated coefficients: The enjoyment of & connection to the coastal environment and visitors' mental health

Figure 9. Model 5's estimated coefficients: The enjoyment of & connection to the coastal environment and visitors' perceived general health

To aid in results interpretation, we generated Figure 10. This figure illustrates the moderating roles of the perceived health outcomes during the previous year's coastal visits. Figure 10a shows that the perceived health outcomes positively moderate the relationship between the enjoyment of and connection to the coastal environment with visitors' mental health in high reliability, while Figure 10b shows the positive tendency of moderating roles of the perceived health outcomes on the relationship between the enjoyment of and connection to the coastal environment with visitors' general health.

4. Discussion

Our study set out to clarify how enjoyment of and connection to coastal environments relate to health outcomes, and the findings offer several important insights. First, consistent with H1, we found that participants who reported greater enjoyment of coastal visits and a stronger connection to nature also reported more positive perceived health outcomes from their coastal experiences. In practical terms, those who really love spending time by the ocean and feel a bond with the coastal environment tended to say that these experiences had noticeably improved their well-being over the past year (for example, helping them feel less stressed, more rejuvenated, or healthier in general). This association aligns with prior qualitative observations that emotionally rich experiences at the coast – feeling at ease, inspired, or “at home” in nature – contribute to individuals' self-assessments of benefit (Severin et al., 2022). Our results extend those observations by quantifying the relationship and showing that it holds across a broader sample. It appears

that how one engages with nature (affectively and cognitively) is a significant predictor of the benefits one perceives; simply put, the more you *enjoy* and *value* the experience, the more you get out of them health-wise.

This study considers feeling physically rested, relaxed, having peace of mind, and feeling happier as perceived health outcomes among visitors to the Belgian coast, specifically, supported by the literature. Somatic or physical complaints are associated with health problems, and physical rest is considered one of the health-related outcomes (Trogakos et al., 2020). Relaxed feeling or being relaxed is associated with subjective well-being or health-related quality of life (Lingli et al., 2017; Merakou et al., 2019). Having peace of mind is associated with subjective well-being and mental health outcomes (Liao et al., 2023; Sophie et al., 2022). Happiness can influence health outcomes and affective, eudaimonic, & evaluative well-being (Diener & Tay, 2017; Steptoe, 2019). The significant positive relationship between enjoyment of coastal environments and perceived health outcomes is evident when examining the frequency of coastal visits; the more often individuals engage with coastal areas, the greater the perceived health benefits they experience.

In examining H2, we also found support for a positive link between perceived health outcomes and actual health measures. Participants who believed their coastal trips benefited their health were more likely to report better mental health, such as lower levels of anxiety and depression symptoms and higher life satisfaction. They also tended to rate their general health more favorably (which in many cases aligned with fewer chronic health complaints or better energy levels). This finding resonates with the literature on self-rated health: perceiving oneself as healthy is often correlated with objective health status and can even predict future health changes (DeSalvo et al., 2006). Here, we specifically tie that perception to coastal experiences – suggesting that if people attribute feeling healthier to something positive they do (like going to the beach regularly), it coincides with measurable well-being. One possible explanation is a behavioral one: individuals who notice benefits might engage more in healthy activities (e.g. more frequent nature walks, physical exercise, stress management techniques), thus improving their actual health. Another explanation is psychological – a person who feels that their lifestyle includes restorative, beneficial activities may have a more positive mindset and resilience, directly bolstering mental health. Our cross-sectional data cannot fully untangle cause and effect, but the strong association is in line with H2 and underlines the meaningful role of subjective outcomes in the nature–health nexus.

Findings are consistent with existing literature that demonstrates the positive impact of blue spaces on mental health, specifically. Previous studies have shown that individuals living closer to coastal environments or visiting frequently experience better mental health outcomes (White et al., 2019; White et al., 2021). In addition, regular exposure to blue spaces, such as coastal regions, has been linked to improved overall well-being (White et al., 2021). Findings emphasize the importance of coastal visits in promoting psychological and physiological well-being, suggesting that regular interaction with coastal spaces is a key factor influencing mental health.

In contrast to the benefits of inland blue spaces, which are primarily centered around physical activity, coastal environments offer unique advantages, particularly in terms of aesthetic and restorative qualities that contribute to mental health (Zhou et al., 2023). While physical activity is often highlighted as a key factor in the mental health benefits of natural spaces, this study indicates that the therapeutic potential of coastal environments extends beyond just exercise. The distinctive sensory experiences provided by coastal landscapes, including the sound of waves, the openness of the horizon, and the tactile sensation of sand likely play a significant role in enhancing mental well-being (White et al., 2021). These findings suggest that the advantages of visiting coastal areas may stem not only from physical activity but also from the broader restorative qualities inherent in these environments.

While the positive effects of visiting coastal areas on mental health are significant, this study found that certain activities, such as feeling the sand beneath one's feet—were not consistently linked to improved health outcomes. This indicates that while spending time in coastal environments may provide psychological benefits, the specific activities performed during these visits might not be as influential as the overall experience of being in nature. The cumulative health benefits may arise from broader community exposure to coastal environments, which could have a more significant impact on public health policies than focusing solely on individual experiences (White et al., 2019).

Further analysis of the relationship between visits to coastal areas and mental health revealed that enjoyment of the coastal environment positively influenced mental health outcomes. Participants reported experiencing a sense of well-being from the vastness of the coast, which contributed to a reduction in mental distress. These findings align with those of White et al., who demonstrated that being close to coastal areas and visiting them regularly is associated with improved mental health, including lower levels of depression

and anxiety (White et al., 2013). Although the effects observed in individual participants were modest, the broader implications suggest that coastal environments offer a unique form of restorative space that facilitates emotional recovery and enhances psychological resilience (White et al., 2013).

Understanding how access to coastal areas affects different socioeconomic groups is important. While studies generally show that frequent visits to the coast can improve mental health, these benefits are not evenly distributed among all demographics. Specifically, individuals from lower-income backgrounds often experience less significant health improvements, indicating that access to nature may not be equally beneficial for everyone (Geiger et al., 2023), or the cumulative effects are different due to diverse visiting frequency. This challenges the assumption that nature-based interventions can uniformly decrease health inequalities and raises significant questions about the accessibility of these resources and the influence of socioeconomic factors on health outcomes.

It is essential to critically evaluate the variability of health benefits associated with coastal visits. While evidence indicates that spending time by the coast can help reduce mental distress, these benefits are not experienced equally by everyone, particularly among marginalized groups. This underscores the need for tailored interventions that consider socio-economic barriers to accessing coastal areas. Previous study supports this notion, suggesting that income-related health disparities may continue to exist, even in nature-based interventions (Geiger et al., 2023). This challenges the idea that exposure to nature has a universally positive effect.

Crucially, the mediational analysis (H3) indicated that perceived health outcomes indeed play a mediating role between coastal enjoyment/connection and health. The statistical mediation tests (conducted via the Bayesian framework) showed that a significant portion of the effect of enjoyment and nature connection on mental health and general health ran through the pathway of perceived benefits. In other words, the reason people who enjoy the coast and feel connected tend to have better health is partly because those people are the ones who *feel* they gain health benefits from their visits, and that feeling is associated with better health status. When we accounted for perceived outcomes in the model, the direct relationships from enjoyment/connection to health outcomes weakened, suggesting indirect influence. This does not nullify a possible direct effect (there could still be some direct physiological benefit of relaxation on health, for instance), but it supports the idea that cognition and perception are key mechanisms in long-term health

impacts of nature. Essentially, the mediational finding bridges the short-term and long-term: enjoyment and connection yield immediate positive experiences; when people internalize those as “this is making me healthier,” it likely reinforces the continuation of nature exposure and also psychologically contributes to well-being, which then reflects in better mental and general health scores. This result validates our use of GITT and the mindsponge concepts (Q.-H. Vuong, 2023; Q.-H. Vuong et al., 2025) – it’s an example of how repeated small positive interactions (and the mind’s absorption of them) translate into a significant overall outcome.

This study is not without limitations. First, the establishment of the causal relationships between coastal enjoyment/connection and health outcomes are limited due to the cross-sectional nature of the data. In addition, the dataset did not consider the pre-existing health outcomes, individual character, psychological problems, weather conditions, and seasonal variations influencing coastal visiting experiences and perceived health outcomes. We recommend Cohort studies to follow up the perceived health outcomes over time following coastal nature exposures, and a more objective measurement of health outcomes will be needed to support the robustness of study findings. Second, the self-reported measures generating the data of perceived health outcomes may promote measurement errors due to subjectivity or personal interpretation, and recall bias. Third, the participants were restricted on Flemish adults and the setting was restricted in the Belgian coast, so findings may be not generalized into different populations, locations, or cultural backgrounds. Future studies may be conducted in diverse coastal settings among various population groups with variations in cultural background to strengthen causal inferences.

5. Conclusions

In conclusion, this study underscores that coastal environments are more than just pretty landscapes; they are valuable assets for public health when people actively engage with them. Enjoyment and a felt connection to coastal nature appear to be key ingredients in unlocking the health benefits of these blue spaces. By examining these factors through both established theories (ART, SRT) and new lenses (GITT, BMF), we provide a richer understanding of the human–nature relationship, one that spans immediate psychological relief to long-term health perceptions. The findings encourage multidisciplinary collaboration – among psychologists, ecologists, public health experts,

healthcare professionals, and urban planners – to design environments and experiences that nurture both people and the planet. As we embrace the idea of an eco-surplus culture, we move towards a future where human wellness and ecological wellness are mutually reinforcing, creating a surplus of benefits for all. The sea, in its vastness, offers not only a mirror to nature’s beauty but also a reflection of our own well-being; recognizing and acting on this interplay could yield profound rewards for generations to come.

6. Implications

6.1. Theoretical Implications

From a theoretical standpoint, these findings have several implications. They reaffirm the value of ART and SRT in explaining the benefits of nature but also suggest that those theories alone do not completely describe the journey from a walk on the beach to year-round well-being. ART and SRT focus on what happens during or immediately after nature exposure (Liu et al., 2024; Ulrich, 2023) – attention is restored, stress is lowered – and our results imply that these immediate effects are indeed happening and recognized by individuals (as evidenced by reported perceived benefits). However, by following up to see associations with longer-term health, we see that the story continues beyond the beach visit. The supportive role of perceived outcomes indicates a cognitive appraisal and encoding process, where people carry forward the effects of the experience in their memory and beliefs. This is where GITT adds explanatory power: our results can be interpreted such that each enjoyable coastal visit provided a unit of positive experience that the mind’s “sponge” soaked up, influencing the person’s internal model of their health. Over time, the accumulation of these experiences could lead to an upward shift in baseline mental health (for instance, consistently lower stress or a more positive emotional tone) and an improved self-care routine (since one might seek out nature or relaxation more regularly). GITT’s notion of granularity and accumulation is reflected in the mediating role of perceived health benefits (Q.-H. Vuong et al., 2025) – it was the aggregation of good experiences, acknowledged by the individual, that linked to better health. Therefore, one key contribution of our study is demonstrating how **short-term** restoration can lead to long-term resilience and improved self-rated health, when viewed through a granular cognitive lens.

The use of Bayesian Mindsponge Framework analytics also proved advantageous. By incorporating the mindsponge mechanism into our model, we were conceptually primed

to look for mediation and cognitive factors, which the results bore out. The Bayesian approach allowed us to estimate the mediated effects with credibility intervals, confirming mediation with a high degree of confidence (the entire posterior distribution of the indirect effect lay above zero). It also handled the complexity of our model (with multiple predictors and outcomes) without issues of divergence or overly strict assumptions. This successful application in an environmental psychology context opens the door for more widespread use of BMF in similar studies. It demonstrates that BMF can capture not only individual decision-making (as shown in previous works on entrepreneurship and religious cognition (Nguyen et al., 2022), but also the subtler formation of health perceptions from cumulative experiences. For researchers, this is a step forward in methodology – providing a template of how to integrate rich psychological theory with robust statistical inference.

6.2. Practical Implications

Beyond theory, our findings carry practical implications for public health and urban planning. One clear implication is that facilitating enjoyable, meaningful interactions with coastal nature could be a viable strategy to enhance community health. City planners and environmental managers should note that it's not only the presence of a park or beach that matters, but how people engage with it. Ensuring that coastal recreational areas are welcoming, safe, and conducive to positive experiences is key. This might involve maintaining clean, aesthetically pleasing beaches, providing amenities that encourage people to spend relaxing time (benches with ocean views, walking paths, guided nature tours), and preserving the natural beauty that elicits awe and connection. Policymakers could leverage these insights by supporting programs that encourage coastal visitation, especially for urban residents who may have limited access. For example, organizing free transport to beaches on weekends, community seaside events, or "blue gym" initiatives can lower barriers to coastal recreation. Health professionals, particularly in mental health care, might consider eco-therapy interventions that incorporate coastal walks or mindfulness on the beach for patients dealing with stress and mood disorders (Summers & Vivian, 2018). Our study suggests that if such interventions succeed in fostering genuine enjoyment and a sense of connection, patients may not only feel better immediately but could internalize those positive effects to build resilience. Indeed, some healthcare providers are already experimenting with "nature prescriptions." The evidence we provide on the benefits of coastal enjoyment could strengthen the case for including blue space experiences in therapeutic regimens.

An important broader impact of highlighting the health benefits of nature is the potential to cultivate an eco-surplus culture. Eco-surplus culture is a concept coined by sustainability scholars to describe a culture in which people actively value and restore nature, going beyond just minimizing harm (Nguyen & Jones, 2022). It embodies a reciprocal relationship: humans invest in nature's well-being and in turn receive surplus benefits (like improved health, joy, ecosystem services). By demonstrating how much the natural environment (in this case, coastal ecosystems) can do for our health, our findings can encourage a cultural mindset that protecting and engaging with nature is an investment in our own well-being. If coastal visits make people healthier and happier, it stands to reason that people might be more motivated to protect coastal environments from pollution, development, and climate threats, to ensure those benefits continue for themselves and their community. Fostering this reciprocal care aligns with building eco-surplus culture – a society that generates a positive feedback loop between environmental health and human health (Nguyen & Jones, 2022). For instance, local governments might channel this by promoting volunteer beach clean-ups or citizen science at the coast as both a community activity and a healthful outdoor experience. Participants not only help the environment but also engage in meaningful activity in nature, further boosting their connection and satisfaction. Over time, as more individuals come to personally appreciate the “health dividend” of nature, the collective attitude may shift towards greater ecological stewardship. This synergy between personal health and environmental responsibility could be crucial in tackling environmental challenges; people are more likely to support conservation policies when they have a personal stake and positive relationship with the natural places being protected.

While our study provides new insights, it also opens several avenues for future research. One direction is to conduct cross-cultural comparisons of these relationships. Cultural background can influence how people perceive and interact with nature – for example, the concept of nature connectedness might vary in meaning across Western and Eastern cultures, or between coastal communities and inland communities. It would be valuable to see if the mediation model we observed holds in different countries or cultural contexts, or if certain cultures derive different types of benefits from coastal environments. Understanding these nuances can inform more tailored interventions worldwide. Another promising avenue is the use of real-time data collection techniques, such as ecological momentary assessment (EMA) (Stone et al., 2023). Instead of relying solely on retrospective reports of perceived outcomes over a year, researchers could use

smartphone apps to prompt people during or right after actual coastal visits to report their enjoyment, mood, and stress levels. This real-time approach can reduce recall bias and capture the immediate restoration as it happens; subsequent follow-ups could see how long those benefits last. Linking EMA data with periodic health surveys could provide a dynamic picture of how repeated visits correlate with trends in mental health over time at the individual level. Additionally, experimental or intervention studies could be designed to test causality: for example, a program that encourages a group of non-visitors to start visiting a local beach regularly (and perhaps includes reflective exercises to boost their enjoyment and connection) versus a control group. Over several months, one could measure differences in perceived health outcomes and psychological health between the groups. Such studies would directly test the mediating process and could also intentionally incorporate components to foster environmental responsibility – linking back to eco-surplus culture. For instance, an intervention might pair coastal recreation with education about marine conservation to see if health improvements coincide with growth in pro-environment attitudes.

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